

Narrative Practices for Children with ASD: Hey! My Therapist Has an Imaginary Friend and Other Anti-tantrum Practices

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Aggressive behaviour is one of the most disruptive problems in children with autism. It generates anxiety in the parents and the child, who does not know what to do, and the family's quality of life is significantly reduced. In this scenario, using narrative practices may help promote the sense of agency in children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and help them find solutions based on self-knowledge. This article explores different narrative practices to help deal with challenging behaviour in children with ASD. We discuss several examples using two techniques: a therapist's imaginary friend and using a magic coin as ways of externalising the problem and playing with metaphors. We present the procedures applied during the interventions with three children. These narrative practices can help to externalise the problem, think about possible solutions, and facilitate the development of imagination and abstract thinking in children with ASD.

Keywords: autism spectrum disorder (ASD), challenging behaviour, narrative therapy, agency, self-knowledge, children

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Narrative therapy places people as experts in their own lives (Morgan, 2000), placing those who are seeking help in the position of 'co-authors' during the therapeutic process (White, 1989). Following White and Epston (1990), we can extract some assumptions from narrative practice. The first is to evaluate the problem separately from the person, assuming the person has many skills, capabilities, competencies, beliefs, values, and commitments that will help them change their relationship with the problems in their life. From this assumption, the practice of externalising emerges. The second assumption refers to the work centered on the person's vital narrative and the selection they make of certain events that make up the plot of their own story, on a temporal level, giving it meaning, and leaving out those that probably do not fit. The third and fourth assumptions refer to the stories and language used in the narrative of life stories. The stories through which meaning is given to experiences are influenced by cultural and social factors, and language serves as a mediator in the interpretative process (Bruner, 1991a, 1991b). The fifth assumption establishes that human beings have lives with multiple stories, so that when faced with the effects of the dominant story that drives or limits the performance of certain acts, we have the capacity to create alternative stories. Thus, the co-creation between the therapist and the consultant of an alternative story to the problem is the key point of narrative practice. It entails incorporating aspects, acts, and people that help to provide a different identity to that which the problem intended, made up of moments when the problem has not had such a strong influence or has not influenced the person at all, the so-called 'unique outcomes' (Chimpén-López & Denborough, 2019; Ingamells, 2016).

Externalising language responds to all the above assumptions and helps to open up spaces for the person's alternative identity (Carey & Russell, 2002; White, 2011). The practice of problem externalisation seeks to allow people to objectify or even personify the very problem that limits them, following the idea of White and Epston (1990): 'the problem becomes the problem, and then the person's relationship with the problem becomes the problem' (p. 40). The therapist transforms this into an intentional practice that is sometimes called 'double listening' to extend externalising away from the problem story and into the preferred story that points to what the person values. Through the use of language, a semantic change occurs that allows the person to evaluate the problem. The therapist is really inviting the person to name the problem for themselves and to evaluate the effects of the experience-near effects of the problem. At the same time, the person can think about the influence they have on the problem and the number of times they have been able to disassociate themselves from its influence (Beaudoin, Moersch, & Evare, 2016; Beaudoin, 2020). From this worldview, narrative therapists focus on the concept of identity built on the continuous experience of interaction with the social environment and which is made concrete in the telling and retelling of the stories that make up our lives.

Narrative therapy applied to children adopts an optimistic vision focused on their skills, capacities, and virtues, without forgetting the use of imagination and play. Separating the child from the problem restores the child's and the family's confidence that the problem can be solved or at least managed. The different ways of interacting, learning, and behaving require the health practitioner to be aware of each child's inside-knowledge (Kemmis & McTaggart, 2008; White, 2007), otherwise it would be difficult to empower them in the resolution of their problems. Internal knowledge is that which the person has in their relationship with the problem because of their lived experiences; a special and unique knowledge (Madigan, 2019). Through the decentred and influential position of the therapist (White, 2007), children are respected as experts of their own lives, providing a context, through conversations, that enables children to become more aware of their own skills and knowledges and how to use these to deal with their difficulties (Ilic, 2017).

Autism spectrum disorder

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a developmental disability according to the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (5th ed; DSM-5; American Psychiatric Association, 2013). It is usually accompanied by other difficulties such as anxiety, depression, challenging behaviours, fears, and sleeping problems, among others. All these conditions can cause significant distress in the children's and their parents' lives, and they can affect the children's identities.

Specifically, individuals diagnosed with ASD are more at risk of developing challenging behaviours than other children (Holden & Gitlesen, 2006). Challenging behaviour is described as a 'culturally abnormal behavior(s) of such intensity, frequency, or duration that the physical safety of the person or others is likely to be placed in serious jeopardy or behavior which is likely to seriously limit use of, or result in the person being denied access to, ordinary community facilities' (Emerson, 2001, p. 3). This conceptualisation includes aggression, self-injurious behaviours, stereotypes, and other destructive or disruptive behaviours, including tantrums. Furthermore, these behaviours create a considerable amount of stress within families, especially for parents, and their quality of life is significantly reduced (De Giacomo et al., 2016; Siu et al., 2019). These behaviours usually generate dominating narratives based on the problem and in which the child is seen as the one responsible for their actions. Children with ASD who exhibit external problem behaviours need more assistance at school, even risking their maintenance in educational placement (Carr, 2016), and their relationships with peers can be damaged, creating a sense of isolation (Yi & Siu, 2021). When parents speak to a practitioner, their story is saturated with the problem. In their narrative, the child is a passive element who becomes the problem.

Some of the most frequent functions of challenging behaviours in people with ASD are to escape from a situation, activity, or place which they do not comprehend or is overstimulating for them, to avoid change, to reject physical contact, to avoid a non-desirable situation, or in response to pain or hyperstimulation (Merino, 2014). Therefore, there are many reasons why a person with ASD can have challenging behaviours.

Since there are so many possibilities, the child's understanding of the problem is crucial to decrease the child's challenging behaviour and even make it disappear. It is crucial to approach the problem while generating a sense of agency in the child. Through play and imagination, through listening to the child's ideas about how to solve the problem using externalising conversations, and by thinking and playing with the child, we can start to create an alternative story (Freeman, Epston, & Lobovits, 1997; Marsten, Epston, & Markham, 2016).

In this article, we explain how we use the narrative therapy theoretical framework to develop two narrative practices, together with the knowledge obtained through these conversations, and our reflections on our experiences during the therapeutic processes.

Examples of Therapeutic Inquiry

Participants

Three stories are presented in this article to illustrate the use of two narrative practices with children with intellectual disability and ASD. Narrative practices were used with these three children, aged between seven and 10, who presented with challenging and aggressive behaviours. They were all receiving weekly individual treatment in a healthcare centre specialising in the treatment of ASD. The sessions were conducted by clinical psychologists (with a master's degree or above) who had experience working with children with ASD and intellectual disabilities. All parents

were informed and accepted the conditions of the study. To ensure confidentiality, the names of the participants, as well as any information which could identify them or their families, have been changed.

Narrative practices

Two narrative practices were used in order to decrease the level of aggressive behaviour of children with ASD: the therapist's imaginary friend and the magic coin. We do not intend to present a comparative study of techniques used in ASD therapy for aggressiveness, but to provide a new perspective based on personal agency and externalisation to complement existing intervention programs.

The therapist's imaginary friend. Epston and Betterton (1993) studied the use of imaginary friends in therapy and how to use them effectively. Chimpén-López (2011) expanded on this idea while working with intellectually disabled children experiencing temper tantrums and referred to the resulting technique as 'the therapist's imaginary friend.' The technique is that, instead of talking directly to the child while they are having a tantrum, the therapist talks to the therapist's imaginary friend. The child observes the conversation between the therapist and their imaginary friend. In this way, it is possible to externalise the tantrum and to separate it from the power that it has in the child's life.

This method is applied when the child is starting a tantrum. At that moment, the therapist, maintaining a prudential distance, begins to talk to their 'imaginary friend.' This conversation must be based on externalising the problem, separating the entity of the tantrum from the child's identity. For this purpose, personifying expressions of the aggressive behaviour are used to give the tantrum a personality and a will, for example, 'the tantrum makes ...,' 'the tantrum wants ...'. At the same time, the therapist's knowledge of the child is used to link them with their positive values and resources, in order to later find strategies to reduce the tantrum. Once this is achieved and the intensity of the episode is reduced, the second part of the technique begins, in which a second externalising conversation together with a re-authoring conversation with the child is used.

Thus, the first part of the technique acts as a distracting factor to reduce the tantrum at its initial point, when it is very difficult to engage in a conversation with the child, acting as a facilitator for the second part once the tantrum has been reduced. The second part is when resources are sought, with the child, to manage the tantrum from the worldview of narrative therapy. We thought that this technique could be applied to children with ASD, and we have used it with positive outcomes.

The magic coin

Chimpén-López (2011) has introduced a narrative practice called *the magic coin* to eliminate bad ideas in a fun way. Like the other practice we have discussed, the magic coin is designed as an anti-tantrum technique and a method to starting externalising conversations as a way to empower children with ASD as well as those who are intellectually disabled. However, in this case, the externalising conversations are centred on the tantrums and on the bad ideas that the tantrums suggest. For this reason, it is not used when a tantrum is in full swing, but when the child has calmed down a bit.

The therapist needs to have a foreign coin (so the child will not recognise it) and to say mysteriously: 'It is said that this is a magic coin. If we keep softly rubbing the coin on a child's head, the coin has the power to absorb the bad ideas that are trying to dominate the child's life.' Then the therapist answers the child's possible questions about the coin, and, with their consent, the therapist rubs the coin on the child's head. After that, the therapist starts to ask externalising questions about the tantrum, for example, when it appears, how it affects the child's life, how it makes the child react. Following this conversation, the therapist talks again about the magic properties of the coin and asks for possible solutions to make the tantrum disappear. Finally, the therapist asks the child what they want to do with the bad ideas inside the coin. Note that the magic coin is simply an instrument to establish conversations that highlight the child's answers in order to contain the tantrum and, in this way, it is the child and not the therapist who proposes the strategies to stop listening to the demands of the tantrum.

This practice has a double intention. The first is to provide a relaxing massage on the child's head so that they will be better able to calm down. The other intention is to take advantage of the quieter situation and use an externalising conversation with the child about what the tantrums and bad ideas want for the child, and even for the child's family. After the externalising conversation, the therapist needs to ask the child what they want to do with the bad ideas that the coin has absorbed. In general, the answer is to throw them away, lock them in a box, or bury them. Again, the child's voice is taken into account as well as recognising the possibility of controlling the tantrums.

Practice Examples and Reflections

Charlie's story: Imaginary friend technique

Charlie was a nine-year-old boy with a diagnosis of level 2 (requiring substantial support) ASD and a 55% degree of disability recognised by the Department of Social Rights from the Spanish government. He presented an impairment in the control of his impulses with hetero-aggressive behaviours such as hitting his classmates or members of his family. He also had problems with perception of time, which made him think that some past events were occurring in the present. This led him to act aggressively in unexpected situations. At other times, he repeated to himself, 'Charlie must not hit,' reproducing the same words that his parents had told him, but his level of comprehension was low. Although he had ASD and a cognitive disability, it was possible to communicate with Charlie. He loved painting and drawing, and he always brought his works of art to therapy sessions. He loved to write all his friends' names in his drawings, and we thought it might be interesting to incorporate his value of friendship in therapy. Therefore, we used the imaginary friend technique when he had a tantrum.

One day, he and his father came to therapy, and Charlie was furious. His father explained to Charlie's therapist that he had broken his cousin's phone, and Charlie tried to hit his father. Charlie did not want to go inside the therapy room, and he was screaming, 'No, I don't want to go!' 'Charlie is bad!' 'Let me go!' His therapist started a conversation with the therapist's imaginary friend while he was still screaming and started talking more or less this way:

What is Charlie doing? You know what? I think that Charlie doesn't want to behave this way. It's the tantrum. I think the tantrum wants him to break things and hit his friends (long pause, like listening to someone). Yes, I think that too. You are right. I think that Charlie doesn't like it (pause). Yes, Charlie wants to be a good friend. He has told me that (pause). Yes, he makes awesome drawings in which he writes all his friends' names. And Charlie knows that a good friend doesn't go away when his friend needs him. I think it's the tantrum talking; the tantrum wants him to be alone (pause). But we won't let it get what it wants (listening again: 'aha,' 'yes,' yes, you are right). For Charlie, his friends and family are very important. He does not want them to be upset. It's the tantrum that makes him hit them. But I know Charlie can beat the tantrum! (pause, Charlie has stopped screaming and he is listening). Of course! Charlie is a good person and a good friend, and he can make the tantrum go away.

After that, Charlie calmed down and listened to the therapist. We went into the study and started talking about the tantrum and how to make it disappear.

Therapist: So, Charlie, why has the tantrum appeared? Charlie: The tantrum came when the phone didn't work.

Therapist: Ah . . . The tantrum likes to break things?

Charlie: 'Yes!' (he makes an angry face). 'And to hit friends.'

Therapist: Do you like what the tantrum makes you do?

Charlie: No, the tantrum is bad.

Therapist: I think we need to beat the tantrum.

Charlie: Yes! Make it go

away! Therapist: How can we

do that? Charlie: Do not know

...

Therapist: In your drawings, you always write down all your friends' names. Do you want to be with them?

Charlie: Yes.

Therapist: Does the tantrum let you be with them and have fun?

Charlie: No ... they run away when the tantrum appears.

Therapist: So, what would you say to the tantrum?

Charlie: That I want to be with my

friends. Therapist: And a good friend

hits his friends? Charlie: No.

Therapist: I think the tantrum doesn't know that. I think the tantrum doesn't know how to be a good friend.

Charlie: I'll say it to stop. And I won't listen to it.

Therapist: That's good!

In past interviews, Charlie was not able to talk about his behaviour, and he just repeated what his parents had told him. He could not do anything about his situation and was a passive actor in the problem. When we started talking about the tantrum, Charlie could talk about it more actively. He started looking for solutions, and the tantrum had less power over him. It was not the last time that Charlie had a challenging behaviour, but he knew that he could win over the tantrum next time.

Albert's story: Imaginary friend technique

We used the same technique with Albert, a nine-year-old boy who did not have language or motor problems but did have an impulse control disorder with frequent tantrums that make him inflict self-harm, with blows to the head, scratches on his face, and hitting things with his head. He was diagnosed with mid/low-functioning autism and a deficiency of 43% as recognised by the government. When tantrums occurred in Albert's life, they also made him throw objects at the people who tried to calm him down, kick them, and break things.

In conversations with Albert during quiet moments, it was clear that one of his ambitions was to be a law enforcement officer, but what he would most like to be is a father. After exploring Albert's idea of being a father and what he would do as a father, we found it interesting to use that information with an imaginary friend when Albert had a tantrum. Albert's tantrum was a result of his unexpected nervousness. After taking him to a private place, the therapist stopped looking at him and started an externalising conversation with the therapist's imaginary friend.

Albert was screaming all the time, 'LEAVE ME! DON'T LOOK AT ME! DON'T TALK TO ME!' So, the conversation with the therapist's imaginary friend responded to Albert's request. The therapist spoke in these terms to his imaginary friend:

'You know, Albert doesn't want to behave like that. That's the tantrum' (pause, like waiting for someone to answer). 'Yes, I agree with you. The tantrum wants him to hurt himself, but he doesn't like that' (pause). 'The tantrum asks us to leave, but a good father can't leave his son's side when he's being attacked by a tantrum' (pause). 'No, we're not leaving either because we love Albert, and we're going to take care of Albert' (pause; the therapist makes nodding gestures). 'You're right, Albert doesn't want us to leave, that's the tantrum trying to make him hurt more. But we're not going to listen to him' (pause, nodding gestures and monosyllables like 'Aha!' 'Yes, yes!' 'Sure!'). 'Besides, Albert wants to be a dad, and we have to help him learn how to do it. When a tantrum has caught a child, and tells the dad to leave, a dad doesn't leave. A dad stays to help the child and tell them that they are good' (pause). 'Albert is good, he is really good.' After another pause, nods and monosyllabic words like 'Aha!' 'Yes, yes!' and 'Sure!'

Albert asked his therapist, 'What did he say to you now?' Logically, he had been calming down and paying attention to the conversation with the therapist's imaginary friend.

After this, Albert and his therapist began to talk about putting aside the tantrum, and not listening to it when it said that Albert had to hurt himself or yell at people who loved him.

Trying to talk to a child who is having a tantrum will probably result in a confrontation rather than help to calm the child. Using the therapist's, caregiver's, or educator's imaginary friend can be a very good way for a child to listen to what is being said without being confronted. And, above all, it can help the child see the effects of the tantrum on themselves, and their families. It also helps the child to choose another way of behaving instead of what the tantrum dictates.

Reflections on using the imaginary friend technique

This technique with children promotes: (a) *listening abilities*: using an imaginary friend can encourage children to listen to what is being said without being confronted; (b) *knowledge of the problem*: it can help them to see the effects of the tantrum on themselves and their families; (c) *self-regulation*: it also helps them to choose another way of behaving instead of what the tantrum dictates; (d) *self-efficacy*: the use of the therapist's imaginary friend helps to communicate more effectively with a child. Thus, due to these related abilities, Charlie and Albert could better comprehend how their tantrums affected them and how to stop or decrease their tantrums.

We believe that this technique goes beyond externalisation, as O'Hanlon (1994) points out. It is a method that allows children to connect with their values and with parts of their identities. In Charlie's story, and in Albert's too, through the conversations with the therapist's imaginary friend and the subsequent conversation with the children, their values of friendship and family emerged, and this helped to stop the tantrum from continuing.

The child's inner understanding begins with their evaluation of the actions which occurred before the conversation with the therapist's imaginary friend. It is not an imposition of the therapist's point of view but a description of what happened. Breaking things and hitting friends is something that has been done under the influence of the tantrum and something Charlie and Albert do not want to do. In the conversation with them that follows, after using the conversation with the therapist's imaginary friend, they can contrast what the tantrum forces them to do with what Charlie and Albert really want to do. With this type of conversation, a space is created for the expression of the child's own motives and understandings.

Anthony's story: The magic coin

Anthony was a 10-year-old boy diagnosed with a moderate intellectual disability and autistic traits. His aggressive behaviour affected his everyday life, requiring him to be isolated in a special education classroom at school. Therapeutic sessions were conducted in his foster home, where he lived due to his mother's difficulties in dealing with her son's aggressive behaviour. In addition to other interventions, the magic coin narrative practice was used.

After breaking a glass during one of his tantrums and considering the consequent risk of physical harm to the other minors who lived with him, he was taken to his room so that he could calm himself more easily. The therapist, without looking into his eyes and when he was more relaxed, took the foreign coin from his pocket (big and shiny) and started to admire it, without showing it to Anthony.

Therapist: Wow! I'm sure that Anthony would love it. How shiny it is! If he was calm enough, I would show it to him ... (looking out of the corner of his eye at Anthony).

Anthony: What is it? Can I see it?

Therapist: Yes, but you have to give me your word that you will not tell anybody, because it's magic.

Anthony: Show me!

Therapist: Do you give me your word?

Anthony: Yes.

Therapist: For sure?

Anthony: I said yes, show me!

Therapist: Ok, but no touching. Look (saying with enthusiasm). It's a magic coin (saying with mystery).

Anthony: No (with his eyes popped open).

Therapist: Yes, it is! It has the power to absorb bad thoughts and bad ideas and make people calm. Do you want to try it to know if it's true?

Anthony: But, will it hurt?

Therapist: No, but you have to give me permission to rub your head with it while you close your eyes. Can you do it?

Anthony: Yes (while closing his eyes).

Therapist: The tantrum tells you to do things other people do not like (rubbing the coin slowly through Anthony's head, like a massage) and it puts ideas into your head that you do not like either. Tell me one so the coin can absorb it.

Anthony: Throwing things.

Therapist: The coin is starting to absorb the idea the tantrum gives you about throwing things away, can you feel it? (moving the coin

softly but a little quicker).

Anthony: Yes.

Therapist: Do you like hurting your classmates or it is something the tantrum makes you do? (slowly moving the coin again).

Anthony: The tantrum, I do not like it.

Therapist: The coin is starting to absorb the idea of hurting your classmates (moving the coin a little quicker again). What else does the tantrum make you do that you do not like? (moving the coin in slow motion).

Anthony: Biting Maria (one of the social educators of the foster home) when I do not like the food and she makes me eat it.

Therapist: Do you want to bite Maria?

Anthony: I do not. I love Maria.

Therapist: What can you say to the tantrum when it tells you to bite Maria?

Anthony: That it leaves me alone.

Therapist: What could you do to stop listening to the tantrum?

Anthony: Cover my ears.

Therapist: And when it tells you to bite Maria?

Anthony: Do not do it.

Therapist: Could you say something like this? 'No, tantrum, I'm not going to bite Maria, she loves me, and I love her.'

Anthony: Yes.

Therapist: Then wait (starting again to move the coin, slowly but quicker): coin, absorb the idea to bite Maria and put the idea in Anthony's mind that Maria loves him and that he says no to the tantrum. (Moving the coin slower again, stopping and taking the coin off the kid's head.) Here they are: the bad ideas the tantrum gave you, like biting and throwing things. What do you want me to do with the coin that contains these bad ideas?

Anthony: To throw it far away.

Therapist: What do you think about downloading the bad thoughts in a place far far away from here and I save the coin in case we need it again to help you?

Anthony: Okay.

It is the bad ideas that are externalised, not the coin. The coin is another ally of Anthony so that he can get the bad ideas out of his life. For this reason, the child must be helped to understand which bad ideas are used by the tantrum to force him to go against his own principles and values. These bad ideas, and not the coin, are the enemy to be avoided. An ally cannot be thrown away, but bad ideas can. In later conversations with the child, it is necessary to make him understand and to open ways towards the search for more allies against the bad ideas and the tantrums.

Reflections on the magic coin technique

With the magic coin technique as one of the possible therapeutic ways to play with metaphors, the child can contribute ideas about how to handle the tantrum. The coin becomes part of the anti-tantrum team, and it is a facilitator to begin conversations about the tantrum and its management. The good ideas children generate while discussing what they can do to control their behaviour are reinforced and repeated so that they can control the tantrum and gain access to their own resources. The next time a tantrum suggests something bad, it can be resisted. The magic coin technique is an aid to assist the child in finding his own resources and learning to manage the tantrum. Once these resources and tantrum management are learned, the use of the coin is gradually reduced, as the need to use this aid becomes less needed.

Educators, parents, therapists, and children can use the coin if necessary. Children who have learned the process can even rub their own heads to relax without the coin. It is recommended that if parents or professionals use this method, they should always ask the child's permission before starting, and then talk about the times the child has managed to resist the tantrum's suggestions. Any type of coin that the child does not recognise can be used, even plastic coins that can be found in some board games.

Discussion

One of the biggest challenges in working with children who present with aggressive behaviours is to keep the problem externalised from their identities. Parents, teachers, and healthcare professionals tend to have discourses that centre on the child as the problem. We have found that this posture does not help a child to be proactive and to be engaged in changing their behaviour. Thus, these discourses can have a negative

effect on the child's self-identity, leading the child to think that they are the problem. In addition, children with ASD have difficulties understanding social relationships and regulating their emotions, and these can make it even harder for them to comprehend their problems and find solutions.

While working with people with autism, it can be easy for a professional to fall into an 'expert' position. However, people with ASD have their ideas and they can find creative solutions to their problems. Children with ASD might have difficulties expressing themselves and talking about their problems, but if we find a way of interacting with them and using their knowledge and interests, the possibilities become infinite. Thus, it is important for practitioners to be mindful and not to take the role of the 'all-knowing expert.' Constructing solutions and talking about the problem in different ways, in a de-centred and influential position (White, 2007), facilitates the involvement of children with ASD as active participants who have their own voices.

The techniques discussed above are creative attempts to honour children's voices in a context in which adults do not usually listen to them or tell them what to do. Narrative practices allow professionals to think creatively, and to start a dialogue between the child and the practitioner. In our experience, when we have given them the opportunity, children with autism have used creative methods to deal with their problems and have shown that they can think about solutions. At the same time, these practices can help facilitate the use of imagination and abstract thinking, skills which might be challenging for some of these children.

This article offers a different view of children with aggressive behaviours that enhances their personal agency, empowering them and offering a different identity than the tantrums intended. The two techniques presented may be useful for professionals who are already implementing treatment programs for child aggression in ASD, but with a different vision, separating the child from the problem and empowering their own internal knowledge about their situation. By letting 'the problem be the problem,' kids can think about solutions and not feel guilty or encapsulated in a role; they are able to see themselves as something other than the problem. In this early period of their lives, when their identities are still forming and changing, it is of the utmost importance to keep children with ASD from pathologising their condition. Kids with ASD are still kids, with their own identities, tastes, and interests, and their own stories.

Our initial therapeutic inquiry offers the basis for future research, and further studies would benefit considerably from having a larger sample of participants in different contexts and with different professionals to obtain a broader vision of the topic. Furthermore, the explanatory nature of the review also represents a limitation in terms of the possibility of generalising the results. Therefore, a critical next step will be to have valid measurement instruments to determine the specific efficacy of the intervention, as well as its long-term effects, with the aim of using these techniques as a complement to other already standardised interventions.

Note

- * This study was carried out under the work's ethics for intervention in minors of the Spanish government. Consent was obtained during recruitment from the legal guardians of the children involved in the study.

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